

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B102
Date: 14 Jun 2005
Take Off 07:52:46 13:37:03
Landing: 12:04:45 16:34:50
Flight Time 4h11m59 2h57m47

Campaign: AMPEP

Trials Instructions:

Operating Area: Circumnavigate via Cranfield, south Wales, uk south and east coast to Newcastle.

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Eiko Nemitz	CEH
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
7	Mission sci trng / bags 2	Ute Skiba	CEH
8	Core Chemistry / TDLAS	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
9	CVI	Paul James	FAAM
10	Filters	Maureen Smith	FAAM
11	CVI Training	Stuart Heath	FAAM
12	PTRMS	Anne Hulse	UEA
13	CCM Training	Jackie Mulholland	Directflight
14	WAS / PAN	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
15	Bag Sampling 1	Debbie Polson	CEH
16	AMS	Johnny Crosier	Manchester University
17	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B102 Track 14-JUN-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b102

Date: 14/06/05

Project: Ampep

Location: wales, south coast, east coast to newcastle. Anticlockwise.

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
074200		engine start	0.49 kft	128	
074219		inu to nav	0.49 kft	128	
074558		taxy start	0.49 kft	128	
075246		T/O	0.48 kft	212	from cranfield
080658		asp open	10.0 kft	246	
082921	083809	Profile 1	10.0 - 1.3 kft	252	
083816	085225	Run 1	1.2 - 1.3 kft	219	
085411	090201	Run 2	1.1 kft	064	
090224	090416	Profile 2	1.1 - 0.13 kft	058	
090417	092534	Profile 3	0.13 - 0.20 kft	059	
090429		Profile 3	0.20 kft	059	interrupt 100ft
090558		Profile 3	0.23	059	resumed
090637		Profile 3	0.61 kft	060	interrupt 500ft
090813		Profile 3	0.56 kft	134	resume
090953		Profile 3	2.1 kft	143	interrupt 2000
091053		Profile 3	2.1 kft	137	resume
091300		Profile 3	4.0 kft	140	interrupt 4000
091404		Profile 3	4.0 kft	140	resumed
091605		Profile 3	6.0 kft	139	interrupt 6000
092623	092951	Run 3	6.0 kft	089	
092951	093459	Profile 4	6.0 - 1.1 kft	091	
093459	093911	Run 4	1.1 kft	092	
093944	095315	Run 5	1.1 kft	038	
095350	100809	Run 6	1.1 kft	094	
100830	101955	Run 7	1.1 kft	052	
102022	103312	Run 8	1.1 kft	005	
103333	104604	Run 9	1.1 kft	354	
104604	105718	Run 10	1.2 kft	287	
105808	111729	Run 11	1.2 kft	305	
111729	114840	Run 12	1.2 - 1.3 kft	325	
115926		asp closed	4.4 kft	180	
120445		Land	0.48 kft	246	at newcastle
120919		standstill	0.51 kft	206	55'02.00N, 1'41.93W
132623		engine start	0.50 kft	206	
133102		taxy start	0.50 kft	206	
133703		T/O	0.48 kft	245	from newcastle
133958		air sample pipes	5.8 kft	017	
135054	135151	Run 13	5.4 kft	017	
135202	140124	Profile 5	5.4 - 0.4 kft	322	
135254		Profile 5	4.4 kft	318	interrupt 4000
135534		Profile 5	4.4 kft	316	resume
135738		Profile 5	2.3 - 0.30 kft	166	interrupt 2000
135839		Profile 5	2.3 kft	153	resume
140137	140231	Run 14	0.37 - 0.38 kft	165	100 ft run
140231	140321	Profile 6	0.44 - 0.76 kft	161	
140321	140429	Run 15	0.76 - 0.92 kft	159	500 ft run
140429	140521	Profile 7	0.92 - 1.3 kft	170	
140521	141501	Run 16	1.3 - 1.2 kft	161	
141526	143115	Run 17	1.2 kft	150	
143115	145050	Run 18	1.2 - 1.1 kft	151	
145129	150216	Run 19	1.1 kft	158	
150216	151711	Run 20	1.1 kft	177	
151711	153231	Run 21	1.1 kft	185	
153612	154244	Run 22	1.0 - 1.1 kft	005	
154311	154526	Profile 8	1.1 - 0.11 kft	009	
154526	155732	Profile 9	0.11 - 6.0 kft	017	
154550		Profile 9	0.20 kft	013	interrupt
154640		Profile 9	0.16 kft	014	resume
154729		Profile 9	0.54 kft	012	interrupt
154816		Profile 9	0.56 kft	007	resume

155000	Profile 9	2.1 kft	319 interrupt 2000
155059	Profile 9	2.1 kft	322 resume
155307	Profile 9	4.0 kft	321 interrupt 4000
155415	Profile 9	4.0 kft	323 resume
155624	Profile 9	6.0 kft	321 interrupt 6000
162446	asp closed	4.5 kft	244
163450	Land	0.43 kft	217 at cranfield
163818	standstill	0.42 kft	307 52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

Sortie Brief: AMPEP

Flight Number : B102

Mission Scientist: Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Date 14-June-2005

Outline schedule:

05:00 – Power to aircraft – warm-up
07:00 – Briefing
08:05 – Clear aircraft and security check
08:20 – Doors close
08:50 – Take off Cranfield
12:50 – Land Newcastle for refueling; Ute Skiba takes over as Mission Scientist
14:15 – Take off Newcastle
16:55 – Land Cranfield
17:25 – Debrief
18:55 – Power down

Location: Anticlockwise circumnavigation of England, Wales

Sortie Aims: To measure the UK pollutant budget of a range of gases and aerosols through a round-Britain flight and to derive the chemical processing (gas/aerosol partitioning & oxidation state) of the air mass in Westerly airflow over the UK. The frontal activity to the North and West limits the area of the UK over which we can work to Southern Britain, but this includes the major pollutant source areas.

Sortie Summary: The budget measurements will be based on a circumnavigation of England, Wales, hugging the coastline along a pre-defined flight path. Vertical profiles (50 – 6000 ft) once upwind and twice downwind of the source region. These should clearly extend into the free troposphere (Mission Scientist to verify from profiles of humidity, temperature and CO). Vertical profiles inside the main plumes will need to be avoided and the location of the profiles is therefore to be confirmed during the flight. These measurements will establish the upwind concentration, the concentration differential at the top of the boundary layer and the concentration in the outflow from the source region. Flight ceiling will be 10000ft. Cabin pressure will be maintained at 1200ft, to minimize expansion of the Tedlar bags.

Sortie Detail with approx timing

- a) Take off Cranfield 10:00 and climb to 10000 ft for transit to upwind leg of the operating area. Destination waypoint 49 in the SW approaches, West of the Bristol channel; background filter run & NO_x calibration.
- b) T+60 descend to 1000 ft when reaching the coast East of point 49. Start of filter run No 2. Start of Bag sampling (1 bag every 2 mins).
- c) T+75 upwind profile while crossing Cornwall starting between WP 47 and 48 (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- d) T+90 descend to 1000ft on reaching the Channel Coast. Start of filter set No 3.

- e) T+145 at point 42: start filter set No 4; increase bag sampling to 1 bag / minute.
- f) T+240 land Newcastle
- g) T+325 T/O Newcastle
- h) T+335 downwind profile heading north (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration)
- i) T+350 U-turn at WP77; start of filter set 4.
- j) T+450 on leaving coast near WP42; downwind profile heading north (dip to 50ft, ascent at 1000 ft min⁻¹, level out at 100, 500, 2000, 4000, 6000 for 1 min each, approx. 15 min profile duration); followed by NO_x calibration
- k) T+ 485 Land Cranfield

Crew List:

1. Pilot 1 - Alan Roberts
2. Pilot 2 – Alan Foster
3. CCM - Gaynor Ottaway
4. CCM Training – Jackie Mulholland
5. Cloud Physics / CCM2 – Paul James
6. Flight Manager – Alan Woolley
7. Mission Scientist – Eiko Nemitz
8. Core Chemistry/TDLAS – Ruth Purvis
9. Filters – Maureen Smith
10. CVI – Paul James
11. CVI Training – Stuart Heath
12. WAS/PAN – Maria Nielsdottir
13. Bag Sampling 1 – Debbie Polson
14. Bag Sampling 2 / Mission Scientist Training – Ute Skiba
15. AMS – Johnny Crosier
16. PTRMS – Anne Hulse
17. NO_x – Dave Stewart

MAPS:

Flight plan for 14th June 2005 AMPEP starting in the SW approaches and tracking anticlockwise

10 pm T/O Cranfield
 transit over land, descend to 1000 ft on reachi

49	191195.7	167394.5
47	116386.8	74400.05
37	?	?
48	212243.2	107206.6

profile while flying over land

46	298518.2	13979.75
45	400000	13018.35
44	470663.7	85763.38
43	576650	88268.13
42	645097.8	137444.2
41	654600.3	227050.6
40	655680.8	316271.6
87	643147.3	406652.5
80	536266.2	467295.4
79	453301.3	567595.1

Refuel at Newcastle

profile while flying north

77	415724.3	641489.4
79	453301.3	567595.1
80	536266.2	467295.4
87	643147.3	406652.5
40	655680.8	316271.6
41	654600.3	227050.6
42	645097.8	137444.2

profile on leaving coast, if possible
 Cranfield

Monday 13 June 2005 00UTC ©ECMWF Forecast t+036 VT: Tuesday 14 June 2005 12UTC
 Surface: 2 metre temperature / 30 Metres Wind

Instrumentation strategies & issues:

Filter sampling: Filters will be taken throughout the flight. Filter pack 1 will contain a Teflon filter for trace metal analysis. Filter pack 2 will contain a Teflon prefilter (for major ion analysis), a nylon filter (for HNO₃ & HCl) and an acidified paper filter (for NH₃). Filters will be changed approximately every 30 minutes or when flight conditions change (as advised by the Mission Scientist). Filters are preloaded into cartridges, which need to be handled with gloves and stored in sealed bags immediately. Filter sampling will be suspended during vertical profiles and resumed when FL10 is re-attained. During breaks, filter packs will be isolated by switching off the pump (to minimise evaporation of volatile aerosol components). During initial transfer to the operating area, a set of filters should be loaded into the filter packs, without sampling, to provide a blank value.

AMS: The AMS will be operated continuously during the flight. Monitored masses will include m/z 16, 18, 28, 30, 43, 44, 46, 57 and 64. The inlet remains closed until airborne to minimize contamination during taxi take-off.

Core Chemistry: CO, SO₂, NO and NO₂ will be measured continuously during the flight. CO will be calibrated every 30 minutes at FL10.

Tedlar bags: Tedlar bags will be filled at a flow rate of 6 lpm, filling a bag over a duration of 30 s. Bags will be filled every 3 minutes upwind and every minute downwind of the source region and during each leveling out for a profile step. Bags should be filled to about 90% of their capacity to maximise sample volume. The cabin pressure will be tightly controlled. Bags from first part of flight can be stored in cargo hold for second part.

Aerosol & cloud physics: CN and PCASP are operated continuously.

Core meteorology & state: Are recorded as standard. Video recording of front facing and downfacing cameras.

PTRMS: Operation as normal.

NOxy: Operation as normal; calibration during transits at FL100

WAS: Sampling density and location to be decided.

TDL for CH₄ and CO₂: Operated by FAAM.

Quick-look data: pressure height, lat, long, temp, RH, CN, SO₂, NO, NO₂, O₃, CO

The flight followed the anticipated flight pattern, transiting to the Bristol channel at FL10, then crossing Cornwall to the south at lower altitude and following the coastline anticlockwise to Newcastle, then backtracking the flight to the south of East Anglia before returning to Cranfield. Ute Skiba took over as mission scientist in Newcastle. In contrast to the model (NAME) forecast, which had some outflow towards the SE, outflow from the UK was not encountered until the East Coast was reached well past Dover. The plumes were in general smaller than expected and they were lower on the southbound flight than on the northbound flight. Possible explanations include an increase in windspeed and an increase in convection throughout the day. Rain showers were encountered near Newcastle.

At Newcastle airport there was a delay with connecting the ground power unit. Teeside should be explored as an alternative refueling location in the area, possibly with better service. On the second leg the TDLAS system did not record data and the NO_x system encountered problems. High temperatures on the flight deck and the front of the fuselage again caused problems for staff and instruments.

On this occasion, a filterpack was loaded on the transit to the operation area, but no air was sampled. To improve the characterization of the background concentrations it would be preferable to sample during this outbound transit leg.

Eiko Nemitz, CEH

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** 102

Date 14/06/2005

Page 1 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
7:52					Take-off
					Boundary layer height on $\nabla \rho$ ~ 500 m?
8:05					NO _x eat starts flying slightly faster FL100
8:07:30	FP run 1	starts			→ 8:29
					broken cloud
8:29	Profile 1	from		FL100	→ 4000 ft initially → 1000ft
					note: 2 ppt offset on SO ₂
8:34		cloud top	at	5100ft	} broken cloud
8:36		cloud base	at	2000ft	
8:38	Run 1 @	100 ft			FP Run 2 start
8:42		slightly			wind 265° / 5 m/s
		no SO ₂ or NO _x		CH ₄	4000 cm ⁻³
8:47		ship plume	on	CO ₂ ?	- change in air mass?
8:49		passing too	ships	on the	right.
8:52		end of run 1:		FPs	keep sampling; run @ pt 4?
8:54		start of run 2	@	1000 ft.	
9:02		end of run 2			; stop of FP run 2
					profile down to 50
9:04:29	run	1	@	100 ft	
9:07	run	2	@	500 ft	
9:09	run	3	@	2000 ft	} over land
9:13:00	run	4	@	4000 ft	
					cloud top @ 6000 ft
					not much convection (flat cloud top)

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B**...102.....

Date ...14/06/05.....

Page ...2 of ...4...

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:25	end R3	6000			@ PT 46
09:26:23	R3	6000			46 → 45
					plenty of ships below us on Channel
09:29:59	P4	6000 → 1000			
09:34:00	R4	1000			7 us before PT 45 / FP run 3 start
09:39:44	R5	1000			new run @ PT 45
09:40					1-minute peak → ship plume 2 also sig @ 45°
					PCASP - one clean high AFS 80% 45000 CN
9:53	R6	1000			@ PT 44
9:55					small NO _x increase
9:58					ship dumping sewage (?) to the right elevated concs NO _x , SO ₂ → effect of cont. Europe?
10:08	R7				@ PT 43
10:20	R8				@ PT 42 end of FP run 3
10:31					start FP run 4
10:33	R9				@ PT 41 225° / 8 m/s
10:37					persistent elevated NO ₂ & CO
10:39-40					quite in focus supply to SO ₂
					10:15 - 10:40 CO & NO highly correlated
10:46	R10				@ PT 40
10:58	R11				elevated CO, NO ₂ , CN
11:10					massive CN & SO ₂ (downwind from Ruspae Dorcasth)
11:17	R12				@ PT 38
11:20 - 11:21					Rain started → drop in concentrations

Mission Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B** 102

Date 14/06/05

Page 3 of 4

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:22	1128	1000 showers			
11:30					420 ppb CO - confirmed
11:46	48				showers
11:48					end of Run 12 & FP Run 4
13:30	showers				start at Newcastle to 6000f
13:50	profile				5000 - 4000
13:54					WS 6 m s ⁻¹
13:55					4000 feet.
13:57					2000 feet. 6 m s ⁻¹
13:58	profile to 50 feet.				increase in CO
14:00					500 f 2 m s ⁻¹
14:01					300 f 3 m s ⁻¹
14:05					1000f CO peak
14:08	FP 1 started				WS 5 m s ⁻¹
14:10					immense in ENC, shower on right
14:15	loaded point 79				WS 12 m s ⁻¹ ships on right
14:16					high particle density
14:19	chimney				increase in CO + particles 13 miles away
14:22	Whitby				
14:26	clearly				clean air (CNC, NOx, CO, SO ₂) 15 m s ⁻¹
14:31	end of run 17				arrived at point 80 high NOx + SO ₂
14:35:30	ships close by				increase in NOx
14:39	immense in				CNC also NOx + SO ₂
14:42	large CO peak				WS 13 m s ⁻¹ also increase in NOx/SO ₂

FLIGHT NUMBER: B102	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP	
PROJECT: AMPEP			

CORE CHEMISTRY PRE FLIGHT LOG

PRE POWER UP	
All sample lines are connected to the rack	OK
All cylinders pressures are OK	OK
Ozone Span = 504, Offset = 50	OK

GAS PRESSURES	N ₂ (bar)	CO ₂ / Argon (bar)	CO standard (bar)
PRE FLIGHT			
POST FLIGHT			

POST POWER UP - GROUND				
Ozone Sample Flow 1 (LPM)	Ozone Sample Flow 2 (LPM)	NO _x Sample Flow (LPM)	NO _x Ozonator Flow (LPM)	SO ₂ Sample Flow (LPM)
CO Time check against HORACE	CO Lamp Flow (ml/min)	Pressure Monochromator (bar)	Pressure Cell (Torr)	

ZEROS							Average
Ozone (ppbV)	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-1	
NO (ppbV)	11.7	10.6	11.2	12.3			
NO₂ (ppbV)	16.1	17.4	17.1	14.8			
NO_x (ppbV)	27.8	28	28.2	27.1			
SO₂ (ppbV)	2.88	2.78	2.68	2.96	2.48		

PRE FLIGHT COMMENTS
Purafil requires changing in zero trap

FLIGHT NUMBER: B102	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP	
PROJECT: AMPEP			

CORE CHEMISTRY CALIBRATION AND FLOW LOG

PREVIOUS CO CAL	Date and Flight Level	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)
	unknown			

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
	100	77.66	89.76	6970.86	50		
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.85	0.6	0.7	1.079	0.067	0.355
084204	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		78.74	88.85	6996.59	50	7.12	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.95			1.112	0.069	0.465
093901	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.26	87.11	6991.22	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		3398	0.4	0.4	1.118	0.067	0.467
101219	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.52	86.88	6995.54	50	7.15	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.93	0.4	0.4	1.118	0.067	0.467
104731	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		80.36	86.45	6947.23	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.95	0.4	0.4	OK	OK	Ok
BAD CAL		CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
14:08:13	1000ft	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		74.92	89.42	6698.71	50	7.13	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.82	035	0.4	OK	OK	OK

FLIGHT NUMBER: B102	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP
PROJECT: AMPEP		

Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
144040	1000ft	76.26	88.75	6767.97	50	7.12	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.89	0.4	0.4	1.107	0.067	0.464
Time	Flight Level	CO					
15:15:22	1000ft	Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		77.35	87.42	6761.94	50	7.14	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
		33.85	0.4	0.4			
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
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Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
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		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample
Time	Flight Level	CO					
		Sensitivity (Hz/ppbV)	Bkgrd (ppbV)	Bkgd Cnt R (Hz)	Lamp Temp (°C)	Cell Press (Torr)	
		Flows (LPM unless stated)					
		CO Lamp Gas (ml/min)	Ozone Sample 1	Ozone Sample 2	NO _x Sample	NO _x Ozonator	SO2 Sample

FLIGHT NUMBER: B102	DATE:	OPERATOR: RMP	
PROJECT: AMPEP			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG

GENERAL COMMENTS

CLoud PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B102

Date: 14/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 1 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:29:31			Not asked For	Not asked For	NAF	NAF	NAF	NAF	NAF	NAF	Start Profile Decent FL100
											FL90
08:31:	130	0.07									FL80
08:32:30	97	0.08									FL70
08:33:25	60	0.08									FL60
08:34:23	363	0.49									FL50
08:35:16	274	0.09									FL40
08:36:22	365	0.1									FL30
08:37:16	314	0.1									FL20
08:38:10	280	0.09									1000ft end of profile
08:38:10	280	0.09									Start of run 1 @ 1000ft
08:40:00	288	0.09									
08:42:00	284	0.09									N.B. Heater left off as all low level
08:44:00	238	0.09									
08:46:00	211	0.09									
08:48:00	195	0.09									
08:50:00	257	0.1									
08:52:00	225	0.1									
08:53:26	213	0.09									End of run1 @
08:54:08	223	0.11									Start run 2 @ 1000ft point 47
08:56:00	218	0.09									
08:58:00	244	0.09									
09:00:00	257	0.09									
09:02:00	228	0.1									End of run 2
09:02:24	230	0.09									Profile 2 1000ft
09:03:26	238	0.09									500ft
09:04:16	304	0.09									50ft
09:04:28	359	0.09									Start Run at 100ft
09:06:00	265	0.09									start profile 3 @ 100ft
09:06:30	123	0.09									500ft interrupt P3
09:07:15	235	0.09									Start run 500ft
09:08:13	369	0.09									Restart P3 @ 500ft

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B102

Date: 14/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 2 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
09:09:00	166	0.09									1000ft
09:09:53	158	0.09									Interrupt P3 start run @ 2000ft
09:10:53	227	0.08									Restart P3 @ 2000ft
09:11:58	207	0.1									3000ft
09:13:01	140	0.1									Interrupt P3 start run @ 4000ft
09:14:02	195	0.09									Restart P3 @ 4000ft
09:15:07	133	0.09									5000ft
09:16:03	367	0.46	In cloud								Interrupt P3 start run @ 6000ft
09:25:35	56	0.07									End run FL60
09:26:23	56	0.07									Start Run 3 @ 6000ft
09:28:00	35	0.07									
09:29:51	31	0.09									End of Run 3 start of P4 descent
09:30:52	243	0.1									5000ft
09:31:52	271	0.1									4000ft
09:32:52	263	0.1									3000ft
09:33:49	424	0.09									2000ft
09:34:59	408	0.09									1000ft end of P4 start of Run 4
09:36:00	364	0.08									
09:38:00	323	0.08									
09:39:12	287	0.08									End of Run 4 @ 1000ft
09:39:45	1620	0.07									Start run 5 @ 1000ft
09:41:00	222	0.07									
09:43:00	280	0.08									
09:45:00	292	0.08									
09:47:00	307	0.08									
09:49	298	0.08									
09:51	314	0.07									
09:53:15	337	0.08									End of run 5 @ 1000ft
09:53:50	362	0.08									Start of Run 6 @ 1000ft
09:55:00	354	0.08									
09:57	321	0.08									
09:59	363	0.08									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B102

Date:14/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 1 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:01	354	0.08									
10:03	256	0.08									
10:05	274	0.08									
10:07	264	0.08									
10:08:05	292	0.08									End of run 6
10:08:30	284	0.08									Start run 7 @ 1000ft
10:10:00	242	0.08									
10:12:00	291	0.08									
10:14	257	0.08									
10:16	431	0.08									
10:18	445	0.08									
10:19:56	475	0.08									End run &
10:20:22	443	0.08									Start run 8 @ 100ft
10:22:00	482	0.08									
10:24	453	0.08									
10:26	361	0.08									
10:28	389	0.08									
10:30	395	0.08									
10:32	412	0.08									
10:33:13	417	0.08									End of run 8
10:33:34	338	0.07									Start of run 9 @ 1000ft
10:35:00	473	0.08									
10:37:00	459	0.08									
10:39	454	0.08									
10:41	428	0.08									
10:43	308	0.08									
10:45	401	0.08									
10:46:04	410	0.08									End of run 9
10:46:04	Not	called	No log until	Data look	Uniform @	approx	300				Start of run 10 @ 1000ft
10:56:00	246	0.08									
10:57:18	432	0.08									End of run 10
10:58:09	287	0.08									Start of run 11 @ 1000ft

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B102

Date:14/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 3 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:50:45	133	0.19									Start Run 5000ft
13:51:45	141	0.32	In cloud								End run start P5 descent @ 5000ft
13:52:55	278	0.13									P5 interrupt 4000ft start run
13:53:56	240	0.52									End run
13:55:25	97	0.2									Restart P5 @ 4000ft
13:56:32	248	0.09									3000ft
13:57:38	222	0.09									P5 interrupt 2000ft start run 13
13:58:40	316	0.1									End run
13:59:45	290	0.09									Restart P5 1000ft (down to 50ft)
14:01:30	246	0.09									End P5 start Run 14 at 100ft
14:02:33	265	0.09									End run 14
14:03:16	123	0.09									Start run 15 @ 500ft
14:04:25	253	0.09									End run 15
14:05:15	201	0.09									Start run 16 @ 1000ft
14:07:00	268	0.2									
14:09:00	152	0.08									
14:11:00	245	0.08									
14:14:55	95	0.09									End of run 16
14:15:26	98	0.09									Start run 17 @ 1000ft
14:17:00	116	0.09									
14:19:00	164	0.09									
14:21:00	172	0.09									
14:23:00	290	0.09									
14:25:00	225	0.09									
14:27:00	310	0.09									
14:29:00	648	0.1									
14:31:00	479	0.1									
14:31:16	326	0.1									End run 17 & start run 18 @ 1000ft
14:33:00	326	0.09									
14:35:00	352	0.09									
14:37:00	394	0.09									
14:39:00	403	0.09									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B102

Date:14/06/05

Operator: JT

Page 4 of 5

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:41:00	365	0.1									
14:43:00	393	0.1									
14:45:00	379	0.09									
14:47:00	368	0.08									
14:49:00	439	0.09									
14:50:51	644	0.09									End of run 18
14:51:30	594	0.09									Start run 19 @ 1000ft
14:53:00	595	0.09									
14:55:00	641	0.09									
14:57:00	468	0.09									
14:59:00	559	0.09									
15:01:00	496	0.01									
15:02:15	547	0.09									End run 19 & start run 20 @ 1000ft
15:04:00	414	0.09									
15:06:00	486	0.08									
15:08:00	498	0.08									
15:10:00	553	0.08									
15:12:00	602	0.08									
15:14:00	590	0.08									
15:16:00	595	0.08									
15:17:08	582	0.08									End run 20 start run 21 @ 1000ft
15:19:00	672	0.08									
15:21:00	479	0.08									
15:23:00	425	0.08									
15:25:00	429	0.08									
15:27:00	416	0.08									
15:29:00	394	0.08									
15:31:00	387	0.08									
15:32:32	255	0.07									End of run 21
15:36:12	252	0.07									Start run 22 @ 1000ft
15:38:00	355	0.09									
15:40:00	373	0.08									

Flight No. B102

Route Antidote *wise circumnavigation
Eng Land & Wales*

Date 14-06-05

Take Off 8:45

Bag Samplers: Dobie / UK

Sheet No. 1

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
8:05					
08-516	8:08	8:08			
08-516	08:10:20	08:10:49			above clouds.
05-047	08:14:15	14:47			"
246	08:18:00	18:31			"
489	08:22:04	18:25			
364	08:26:00	26-23			
494 489	08:28:20	29-50			Profile 1
051	08:30:20	30:38			"
406	08:32:00	32:28			"
441	08:34:00	34:28			in cloud
048	08:36:00	36:26			below cloud 1000
427	08:37:00	37:28			"
044	08:38:00	38:30			End of profile + 1000 feet
310	08:40:00	40:30			
435	08:42:00	42:29			
30	08:44:00	44:30			slightly hazy.
054	08:46:00	46:30			
489 451	08:48:00	48:29			
183	08:50:00	50:29			
046	08:52:00	52:27			profile to 50 feet
045	08:54:00	54:30			standard
043	08:58:00	58:30			10.2 °C
250	9:00:00	4:00:29			
022	9:02:00	02:30			
0245	9:04:11	04:30			at 70 feet
122	04:44	05:13			at 100 feet
545	9:05:56	06:21			start climb to 500 feet
436	9:07:07	07:36			at 500 feet
085	9:08:14	08:42			climb to 2000
089	09:08	09:30			
518	09:52	09:10:21			2000 feet standard
24	10:54	11:24			profile climb to 4000
79	10:43	12:11			
557	13:00	13:30			start run
78	14:00	14:30			
4	14:46	15:16			in cloud.
80	16:02	16:32			6000 feet
285	18:30	19:00			"
73	21:00	21:30			"
124	24:30	25:00			"
	25:00	25:30			

run 1
start
at
1000 feet

run land
almost
at point
37

end of
profile

Flight No. 13102Route

England/Willy

Date 14-06-05Take Off Bag Samplers: Ute DebyeSheet No. 2

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
282	09:27:00	09:27:00			6000 feet
83	09:29:30	09:29:57			
185	30:25	09:30:00	5300	5800	profile to 1000 feet
190	31:30	32:00	4300	3700	
290	32:30	33:00		2800	
424	33:30	34:00		1700	
370	34:30	34:57	1200	1000	end of profile.
27	36:00	36:25	1000 feet		large CO peak.
353	38:00	38:30			
457	09:40:00	40:30			plume of NOx SO2
271	09:42:00	42:30			
363	09:44:00	44:30			
011	09:46:00	46:30			
184	09:48:00	48:30			
077	09:50:00	50:30			Isle of Wights
308	09:52:00	09:52:30			
552	09:54:00	09:54:30			
38	09:56:00	56:30			
203	09:58:00	58:30			
426	10:00:00	10:00:30			
520	10:02:00	10:02:30			
072	10:04:05	10:04:35			
172	10:06:00	10:06:30			
342	10:08:00	10:08:30			end of run to point H3
318	09:00	09:30			
293	10:00	10:30			CO plume.
496	10:00	11:30			
439	12:00	12:30			
016	13:00	13:30			
555	14:00	14:30			
214	15:00	15:30			
015	16:00	16:30			
012	17:00	17:30			
003	18:00	18:30			
178	19:00	19:30			ships Dover (daisy) straits
041	20:00	20:00			
558	21:00	21:30			
253	22:00	22:30			
37	23:00	23:30			
288	24:00	24:00			
245	25:00	25:30			turbulence.

Wind
10ms⁻¹

started

visible

end of run.

H3

straits

End of run
7

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

1000 feet.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
498	10:26:00	10:26:30			
175	27:00	27:30			
517	28:00	28:30			
359	29:00	29:30			Bag is damaged.
28	30:00	30:30			
551	10:30:00	31:30			
314	32:00	32:30			
123	33:00	33:30			leaded point 41 end of run 8
80	34:00	34:30			CO release
241	35:00	35:30			NOx SO ₂
26	36:00	36:30			
255	37:00	37:30			
177	38:00	38:30			CO / NOx release.
40	39:00	39:30			
23	40:00	40:30			low Sulfur.
39	41:00	41:30			SO ₂ sharp peak
455	42:00	42:30			
411	43:00	43:30			
52	44:00	44:30			
49	45:00	45:30			
470	46:00	46:30			end of run 9
70	47:00	47:30			
59	48:00	48:30			big CO peak
68	49:00	49:30			
109	50:00	50:30			
181	51:00	51:30			low Sulfur.
74	52:00	52:30			"
402	53:00	53:30			"
067	54:00	54:30			Crowder
425	55:00	55:30			
249	56:00	56:30			Bag did not fill much
415	57:00	57:30			
430	58:00	58:30			
247	59:00	59:30			
61	11:00:00	11:00:30			
9	11:01:00	01:30			
126	02:00	02:30			
62	03:00	03:30			
13	04:00	04:30			
129	05:00	05:30			
001	06:00	06:30			

with 7ms

32

run 10

end of run 10
point 87
87-80
run 11

Flight No. 13102Route Date 14:6:05Take Off Bag Samplers: Wt DobbleSheet No. 4

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
002	11:07:00	11:07:30			1000 feet
435	11:08:00	11:08:30			mouth of Hudson
252	11:09:00		Downriver	Grimsby	SO ₂ NO _x plume
524	11:10:00	11:10:30			
493	11:11:00	11:11:30			
21	12:00	12:30			
403	13:00	13:30			
007	14:00	14:30			peak of NO _x SO ₂
176	15:00	15:30			
244	16:00	16:30			
127	17:00	17:30			start of run 12
173	18:00	18:30			rise in NO _x plume
511	19:00	19:30			
56	20:00	20:30			
5	21:00	21:30			1200 feet
53	22:00	22:30			SO ₂ NO _x plume
55	23:00	23:30			"
256	24:00	24:30			"
272	25:00	25:30			"
454	26:00	26:30			"
232	27:00	27:30			" well defined CO peak
402	28:00	28:30			
17	29:00	29:30			
64	30:00	30:30			
186	31:00	31:30			not well seen
90	32:00	32:30			
189	33:00	-30			
82	34:00	-30			
75	35:00	-30			
499	36:00	-30			
87	37:00	-30			
6	38:00	-30			(CO + NO _x SO ₂) plume
30	39:00	-30			
84	40:00	-30			
128	41:00	-30			
86	42:00	-30			
58	43:00	-30			
66	44:00	-30			
69	45:00	-30			Plume of NO _x
57	46:00	-30			" Holy Island
071	47:00	-30			

end of run 80

Flamewall head

} turbulent

Flight No. 13102Route Date 14.6.05Take Off Bag Samplers: Use D & S 1/2Sheet No. 5

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
65	11:48:00	11:48:30			end of run 12
60	11:49:00	11:49:30			climb to 5000 feet
descent to Newcastle now.					
To Newcastle 13:37					
626	13:43:00	13:43:30			6000 ft
610	13:50:00	13:50:30			5000 ft
611	13:51:00	13:51:30			6000 ft level
612	13:52:00	13:52:30			5000 → 4000 (500)
613	13:53:00	13:53:30			4000
97	13:54:00	13:54:30			4000
614	13:55:00	13:55:30			4500
615	13:55:45	13:56:15	55°N	1.6W	4000 → 2000 (300)
616	13:56:40	13:57:10			~2000
617	13:57:45	13:58:15			2000
618	13:58:55	13:59:25			~1800
619	14:00:00	14:00:30			~800
620	14:01:00	14:01:30			~500
622	14:01:43	14:02:13			@ 100
623	14:02:40	14:03:10			100 → 500 (*)
624	14:03:30	14:04:00	3W	20°E	@ 500
625	14:04:30	14:05:00			500 → 1000 (800)
621	14:05:20	14:05:50			1000 ft.
95	14:06:20	14:06:50			1000 ft.
98	14:07:20	14:08:00			"
133	14:08:30	14:09:00		5W/8	20°E
132	14:09:30	14:10:00			"
99	14:10:30	14:11:00			"
100	14:11:30	14:12:00	55.0	1.1W	"
91	14:12:30	14:13:00			rain to the west
92	14:13:30	14:14:00			@ PT 79
92	14:14:30	14:15:00			
162	14:15:30	14:16:00			
31	14:16:30	14:17:00			
32	14:17:30	14:18:00			Chinese started to west
161	14:18:30	14:19:00			
86	14:19:30	14:20:00			Chimney upwind
140	14:20:30	14:21:00			
117	14:21:30	14:22:00			
113	14:22:30	14:23:00			
101	14:23:30	14:24:00			
102	14:24:30	14:25:00			1000 ft

in cloud
PRSwest
cement?
→ no
plume
detected

Flight No. Route Date Take Off Bag Samplers: Sheet No.

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
8-103	14:25:30	14:26:00	54.3	0.3 W	1000 ft
104	14:26:30	14:27:00			
105	14:27:30	14:28:00			
106	14:28:30	14:29:00			
108	14:29:30	14:30:00			
107	14:30:30	14:31:00	233°	13 w/s	NOx plume - not very faint
119	14:31:30	14:32:00			@ FT 30
114	14:32:30	14:33:00			
115	14:33:30	14:34:00			
116	14:34:30	14:35:00			Phil elevated 150
117	14:35:30	14:36:00			
118	14:36:30	14:37:00			
109	14:37:30	14:38:00			Ship below
111	14:38:30	14:39:00			
105	14:39:30	14:40:00			
110	14:40:30	14:41:00			
151	14:41:30	14:42:00			
152	14:42:30	14:43:00	53.34	0.5 E	all @ 1000 ft
139	14:43:30	14:44:00			
135	14:44:30	14:45:00			
136	14:45:30	14:46:00			
137	14:46:30	14:47:00			
138	14:47:30	14:48:00			
134	14:48:30	14:49:00			
153	14:49:30	14:50:00			
154	14:50:30	14:51:00	233°	9 w/s	@ 87
155	14:51:30	14:52:00			
156	14:52:30	14:52:00			
600	14:53:30	14:54:00			
601	14:54:30	14:55:00			
603	14:55:30	14:56:00			
609	14:56:30	14:57:00			
608	14:57:30	14:58:00			
607	14:58:30	14:59:00			
602	14:59:30	15:00:00			
606	15:00:30	15:01:00			
605	15:01:30	15:02:00			
604	15:02:30	15:03:00			@ FT 40
157	15:03:30	15:04:00			
158	15:04:30	15:05:00			
159	15:05:30	15:06:00			

elevated
 NO_x & CO
 no SO₂
 ⇒ London
 plume?

Flight No. 2102

Route

Date 14/06/05

Take Off

Bag Samplers: Debbie & Elio

Sheet No. 7

Bag Number	Time on (GMT)	Time off (GMT)	Lat	Lon	Comments
05-16a	15:06:30	15:07:00	52.4N	1.8E	NOx & CO plane
629	15:07:30	15:08:00			"
627	15:08:30	15:09:00			"
628	15:09:30	15:10:00			end of plane
33	15:10:30	15:11:00			
24	15:11:30	15:12:00			
25	15:12:30	15:13:00			
96	15:13:30	15:14:00			
377	15:14:30	15:15:00			
278	15:15:30	15:16:00			wt v. full
344	15:16:30	15:17:00	51.3	236°	@ PT43
284	15:17:30	15:18:00			
354	15:18:30	15:19:00			
352	15:19:30	15:20:00			
378	15:20:30	15:21:00			
28a	15:21:30	15:22:00			
174	15:22:30	15:23:00			
37c	15:23:30	15:24:00	51.5N	1.6E	
350	15:24:30	15:25:00			
379	15:25:30	15:26:00			
164	15:26:30	15:27:00			
461	15:27:30	15:28:00			
141	15:28:30	15:29:00			
143	15:29:30	15:30:00			
525	15:30:30	15:31:00			
166	15:31:30	15:32:00			
163	15:32:30	15:33:00			@ PT42
146	15:33:30	15:34:00			
145	15:34:30	15:35:00			
170	15:35:30	15:36:00			
559	15:36:30	15:37:00			
142	15:37:30	15:38:00			
453	15:38:30	15:39:00			
10	15:39:30	15:40:00			
147	15:40:30	15:41:00	51.3	1.5E	
old 252/262	15:41:30	15:42:00			End of Run
05-168	15:43:30	15:48:00			↑ all @ 1000
428	15:43:35	15:46:05		@ 400	1000 → 2000
149	15:46:35	15:46:55		100 → 500	
438	15:47:05	15:47:40		@ 500	
317	15:48:20	15:48:55		500 → 2000	(N 700)

1000 ft

elevated
NOx

WAS Sampling Summary

Flight Number: B102
Date: 14/06/2005

Campaign Name: AMPEP
Operator: M. Nielsdottir (UEA)

Bottle Start Fill Time	Bottle End Fill Time	Bottle Number	Comments	Final Pressure (bar)
08:29:21			Start Run 1 at 1000 ft	
8:39:05	8:40:05	25	Heading away from 49	3.35
08:42:09	8:43:09	26	Between 49 and 47	3.35
08:46:15	8:47:15	27		3.35
08:52:25			End Run 1	
08:54:11			Start Run 2 at 1000 ft	
09:02:11			End run 2	
09:16:45	9:17:15	28		
09:26:23			Start run 3	
09:26:57	9:27:57	29		3.20
09:34:59			Start run 4	
09:37:32	9:38:32	30		3.36
09:39:11			End run 4	
09:39:45			Start run 5 (1000 ft)	
09:40:11	9:41:11	31	Some polluted air- plume from ship or oil rig? AMS indicated increased levels of sulphur	3.34
09:50:14	9:50:44	32		
09:53:15			End run 5	
09:53:15			Start run 6 (1000 ft)	
09:58:59	9:59:29	1	Increased levels of NOx indicated	3.35
10:08:09			End run 6	
10:08:30			Start run 7 (1000 ft)	
10:19:59			End run 7	
10:20:22			Start run 8 (1000 ft)	
10:20:43	10:21:43	2		3.30
10:28:26	10:29:26	3		

10:33:12			End run 8	
10:33:33			Start run 9	
10:33:50	10:34:50	4	Plume?	3.35
10:35:07	10:36:07	5	Plume?	3.35
10:43:08	10:44:08	6		3.35
10:46:09			End run 9 (1000 ft)	
10:46:04			Start run 10	
10:55:17	10:56:17	7		
10:57:18			End run 10	
10:58:08			Start run 11	
10:58:24	10:59:24	8	Plume	3.35
10:59:35	11:00:35	9		3.35
11:01:10	11:02:10	10		3.35
11:03:48	11:04:48	11		3.35
11:05:16	11:06:16	12	Plume- Pilots report seeing smoke (from cars below?)	3.35
11:09:25	11:10:25	13	Plume	3.35
11:10:34	11:11:34	14	Still in plume?	3.35
11:14:16	11:15:16	15	Plume- different chemical composition	3.35
11:15:51	11:16:51	16	Plume	3.35
11:17:29			End run 11 and start run 12	
11:19:11	11:20:11	17	Increased levels of CO indicated	3.35
11:20:22	11:21:22	18		3.35
11:33:44	11:34:44	19	Plume (400 ppb CO)	3.35
11:43:16	11:44:16	20	Plume	3.35
11:48:40			End run 12	
13:53:17	13:53:47	21		3.35
14:19:03	14:19:34	22		
14:29:15	14:30:15	23	Plume	3.36
14:31:15			Start run 18	
14:32:00	14:33:00	24	High NO _x and CO	3.35

14:37:49	14:38:49	57	Still in plume- high CO	3.36
14:46:31	14:47:31	58	Out of plume	3.36
14:50:50			End run 18	
14:51:29			Start run 19 (1000 ft)	
15:00:01	15:01:01	59	High CO levels indicated	3.36
15:01:18	15:02:18	60	High CO levels indicated	3.36
15:02:16			End run 19 and start run 20	
15:05:41	15:06:41	61	Broad plume (possibly London plume)	3.35
15:07:01	15:08:01	62	Broad plume (possibly London plume)	
15:17:11			End run 20 and start run 21	
15:32:31			End run 21	
15:36:12			Start run 22 (1000 ft)	
15:42:44			End run 22	
15:56:24	15:57:03	63	6000ft	3.19

14th June 2005

Flight B102 - AMPEP

GMT

AMS - Sunny Cruiser.

0500 - No aircraft.

0535 - Aircraft on Pad with power.

0545 - All pump on @ 100%
→ heater on.

CPC on

Balzers on

0610 -
 $I_{elec} = 0.8A$
 $I_{cp} = 3A$
 $I_{sp} = 1.5A$

Heater $V = 23V$

Heater $I = 0.93A$

Heater $T = 422^\circ C$

Chopper = 120 Hz

Pressure = 0.063 Torr

0637 - Filament on @ 0.01 mA

Multiplier reduced from 2.475kV
to 2.00kV.

0643 - reset multiplier to 2.475kV.

Filament @ 0.1 mA.

0655 - Filament @ 2.5 mA.

MS leads good.

0727

-

Turning

		Old	New
Ret	In	20	20
Ret	Ext	11	11
HR		-660	-659
FOC		1625	1610
Ext		212	232

0101-00

0729

-

EM cal

$kV = 2450$
 $U_{an} = 3.5 \times 10^6$
 $U_{change} = -0.025 \times 10^6$

Min range cal

0735

-

IE cal

$IE = 2.32 \times 10^6$
 $K_{S_{ms}} = 2.57 \times 10^6$
 $K_{S_{en}} = 2.27 \times 10^6$

 $IP_{ms} = 534$
 $IP_{en} = 502$

1600 - Home time

changed data by rate @ 5M116
for 207, 413 + 543 mids

1737 - EM cal

$$2J = 2.85$$

$$\text{mean} = 2.92 \pm 0.6$$

1833 - IE cal

$$IE = 1.869 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\text{Mean} = 2.96 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\text{Abs} = 2.01 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$\text{Abs} = \text{ice} \quad R \quad 8 \pm 84$$

$$\text{Runs} \quad 8 \pm 80 = 8 \pm 81$$

* 1854 - like run 8080

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B102**

Date: 14/06/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
GPS		Y	FFSSP	Y	N
Satcom C		Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-P	Y	N
<u>Thermometers</u>			2D-C	Y	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	Cloudscope	N	N
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 1	Y	N
Heimann	N		SID 2	Y	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>					
G. Eastern		Y	HVPS	N	
J. Williams		Y	CIP25	Y	N
Nevzorov		Y	CIP100	Y	N
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
ECGC	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	Y	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	Y
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B102

Date: 14/06/05

Instruments

1. Video – DFC display out of focus. Inboard display switches off . Also, RFC (marked DFC...) is virtually black on pc monitor, whereas it displays well on video monitor unit.
2. NOX – occasional flutters above max chamber temp but otherwise okay.
3. TDLAS CO2 failed 30 mins before the end of the first flight. No data at all from second flight for CH4 either.
4. Horace display of data locked up at 15:50. Couldn't then retrieve data from before this time despite restarting internet explorer and then H_derive.

Aircraft

Satcom H:-